

Design and Implementation of an Automated Drying Line System (ADLS)

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Abstract—Traditional clothes drying lines are unable to protect clothes from rainfall, theft, strong winds, dust, stains, birds dropping and insects. This makes life unbearable. This paper seeks to design a system that will not only help dry clothes but also offer protection of clothes from rainfall, theft, strong winds, dust and stains. The designed system has a tube that directs sun rays from outside into a box-like container within the room which contains the hung clothes. The tube with its converging lens direct sun rays onto a reflecting plane which in turn direct the rays into the box uniformly with the help of a diverging lens. The interior surfaces of the box are coated black to retain heat. The system has a humidity sensor to measure the dryness of clothes and notify the user via an LED blink and the sound of a buzzer. The system has a fan that can be turned on to expedite the drying process of clothes within the system. It goes off automatically when clothes are dried thereby conserving energy. The system receives instructions from Arduino Uno. All codes were written with Arduino IDE.

Keywords— *Serial Arduino, Arduino Nano, Arduino Uno, Arduino 101, LED.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Automation is now common place in recent years mainly because of its ubiquitous nature. It cuts across almost all spheres of life, be it education, industry, health and agriculture. In fact, contemporary life is unconceivable devoid of highly proficient computer systems.

The development of automated system is on the ascendency and this can be traced back to origination of the microprocessor chip in the 1960s. Automation in recent years is not only restricted to information provided or performing of actions, however, it also comprises analyzing information and selecting the right actions.

Automation as a word emanates from two Greek words, namely, “Auto” which means self and “Matos” which means moving. Thus, it is the mechanism for devices that moves on their own. Automation, therefore, can be defined as, “A set of technologies that results in the operation of machines and systems without significant human intervention and achieves performance superior to manual operation” [8].

Existing traditional drying lines are not able to protect clothes against rainfall, dust, strong wind, theft and others. This causes a lot of problems for individuals.

In most organisations and educational institutions, for instance, people lose concentration either at work or class when the weather becomes cloudy while their clothes are on the drying lines. Some people resort to neighbours just to

save their clothes from the touch of rainfall. Others have also suffered injuries in their quest to rush down the stairs to pick their clothes from the drying lines. Those who forget their clothes on the drying lines sometimes find them either stolen or stained with bird’s droppings. There have also been instances where people pick their clothes from the drying lines with dangerous insects hidden in them. Thus, if there exists a smarter drying line that can solve the aforementioned problems, life will be made more comfortable.

This paper seeks to build a drying line system that is capable of protecting clothes from rainfall, theft, strong wind and dust. The already existing systems reviewed so far can protect clothes from rainfall. However, when it comes to protection from dust, strong winds and thefts, these systems do not provide the optimum solution. Hence, the motivation to embark on this paper.

The system shall have two main components. Videlicet a tube that shall convey sun rays into the system and a box-like structure that shall keep the clothes.

A. Types of Automation

There are two branches of automation. These are:

1) *Feedback Control*: It is a constant process that includes recording dimensions with sensors and also calculating adjustments through a controller to an output device. This helps to keep the measured variable within a fixed range. (e.g. water heater). It could be a closed loop or opened looped.

2) *Sequence Control*: It executes diverse actions based on different system states. It may be either a fixed sequence or a logical one. (e.g. elevator) [1].

The types of automation include:

- Fixed automation;
- Programmable automation; and
- Flexible automation

B. Importance of Automation

The benefits of automation as stated by [1] are:

- It decreases the amount of labor;
- Conserves energy through efficiency gains;
- Reduces the number of materials needed;
- Improves accuracy, quality, precision and predictability; and
- Ensures safety by removing humans from unsafe or dangerous conditions.

II. RELATED WORKS

Automated or smart drying lines are systems that are designed to ensure that clothes go through a successful process of drying. This ensures that clothes are well hanged to dry thereby reducing drying time and ensuring the security of clothes.

There are several already existing papers on automated drying lines. In [5] paper, clothes are automatically retrieved out on a sunny day and retrieved in when it is a rainy day. In this system, an Arduino UNO board was used to give instructions to the system via the programs installed on it. A DC gearbox motor moved clothes forward and backwards. A rain sensor circuit was designed and an LDR circuit using the Proteus software.

[6] proposed a system titled “Smart Outdoor Clothing Rack and Curtain Blade Control System”. In this paper, when a rain sensor senses raindrops, it triggers a special protective layer to cover the clothes. This is achieved with the help of two motors. The system was also able to regulate window blades by comparing the brightness of the inner house with that of the outer house.

[2] presented a research paper on the theme “Automatic Clothes Retrieval and Drying System”. A Microcontroller PIC 16F877 was used to install all programs that will give instructions. A temperature sensor was used to measure the temperature conditions whether day or night. LDR (Light Dependent Resistors) was used to measure light. A rain sensor to sense rain and an LCD to display the day condition was used. A dry time for the clothes was set up using a rotary knob switch which automatically retrieve-in the clothes when drying time is finished using a DC motor.

[3] worked on a paper titled “Development of Arduino Smart Clothes Hanger Embedded System for Disabled”. This paper was designed to assist the physically challenged in society during a rainy day. The system automatically pushes out the hanger during sunny days and reversely pulls it in during rainy days. It also had the function of moving the hanger vertically up and down to make it easy for disabled individuals especially those who are wheelchair-bound to hang and retrieve their clothes. The paper required the use of Atmega 328P-PU to install all coding programs to run the system. Voltage regulator LM7805 is also used to regulate the supply at 5V. LDR sensor was also used in this paper. A DPDT switch was also used to connect with the second motor to move the hanger vertically.

[4] worked on a paper titled “Electric Clothes Dryer and Dehydrator”. This paper proposed a machine used for drying clothes as well as food dehydration. The clothes and food dehydrator was designed at the top and bottom of a box. Temperature controllers were used to maintain the desired temperature and fans were used to distribute the heat uniformly. The hot supply airflow through the drying chamber where it absorbed moisture from the wet clothing or foods and heats the clothes and food to stimulate evaporation. Moisture was removed from the chamber by the hot air. The air was drawn through the bottom section as well as the dryer. The air then entered into the ducts and the drying chamber by an exhaust fan, in line with the duct. In the food section, there were two trays provided on which vegetable and fruits slices were kept. The vents were provided to remove water vapour from both sections on the right side of the system.

A. Arduino Models

Arduino was created in the year 2005 in Ivrea Italy as a Master’s thesis project. The idea behind it was to achieve rapid prototyping. That is a less expensive device that can be used to control interactive electronic projects. Its goal was to enable non-technical individuals to develop technical systems of their own. It was named “Arduino” in honour of Bar di Re Arduino. It was assembled around the Wiring project of Hernando Barragan. Figure 1 shows the prototype of Arduino.

Fig. 1. The First Prototype of Arduino [7]

An Arduino is an open-source electronic device that is designed based on easy-to-use hardware and software. It has a microcontroller board that uses diverse kinds of microprocessors and controllers to enable fast prototyping regarding electronics. There are different kinds of models with numerous practical applications.

Arduino comprises of two major components. These are:

- Arduino board. It is a piece of hardware one works on when building objects; and
- Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). It is a software which is run on a computer. It is used to build a sketch (computer program) which is uploaded to the Arduino board. The sketch instructs the board to execute a task.

The available models of Arduino and their release date are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. MODELS OF ARDUINO

Name	Date released	Processor	Frequency	Host Interface
Serial Arduino	2005	ATmega 8	16MHz	DE-9 serial connection
Arduino Nano	May 15, 2008	ATmega 8	16MHz	USB
Arduino Uno	September 24, 2010	ATmega328P	16MHz	USB
Arduino 101	October 16, 2015	Intel Curie	32MHz	USB

"Uno" in Italian means one. It is so named to mark the production of Arduino 1.0. Its digital input and output pins are fourteen (14) in number. Six of these pins can be employed as Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) output pins. It has six analogue inputs. It has a USB connector which is used to communicate with the computer. Arduino Uno has a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, an ICSP header, a power jack and also a reset button. All functionalities needed to support the microcontroller is on the Arduino Uno. Aside from

powering it with a computer, it can also be powered by a battery or an ac-to-dc adapter. Uno does not use an FTDI USB-to-serial driver chip. This feature makes it different from other boards. It comes along with ATmega16U2 programmed as a USB-to-serial converter.

The Uno board works when supplied with an external supply of 6 to 20 volts. If less than 7V, is supplied to it, the 5V pin may produce less than 5 volts. This makes the board unstable. When more than 12V is used, the voltage regulator will become overheated which damages the board. It is therefore recommended that 7 to 12 volts are used. Figure 2 shows an Arduino Uno circuit board.

Fig. 2. Arduino Uno

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The system design of this paper is divided into two main parts. They are hardware architecture and software design. With the hardware architecture, the design of the circuit was constructed and the prototype of the paper was built. The software design was implemented using programming codes.

A. Hardware Architecture

DHT11 is part of the DHTXX family. It is used to measure humidity and temperature. It has four pins namely VCC, Data out, Not connected and Ground. The not connected pin has no usage. This sensor includes a resistive-type humidity measurement component and an NTC temperature measurement component. It connects to a high-performance 8-bit microcontroller. DHT11 offers a fast response, cost-effectiveness and anti-interference ability.

The power supply of DHT11 is 3V to 5.5V DC. Instruction is not directed to the sensor within a second so that the unstable status is passed when power is sent to the sensor. To achieve power filtering, a capacitor whose value is 100nF can be placed between VDD and GND. Figure 3 shows a DHT11 sensor.

Fig. 3. DHT11 sensor

When the DHT11 sensor is made to work beyond the range specified in its datasheet, it can lead to a signal shift of three per cent RH. It can get back to the calibrated mark progressively when it is used again in the normal operating state and made to function within its stipulated range.

The various specifications of the DHT11 sensor is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. SPECIFICATIONS OF DHT11 HUMIDITY SENSOR

ITEM	VALUE
Temperature Range	0-50/+2 or -2 degree Celsius
Humidity Range	20-80%/ + or - 5%
Sampling Rate	1Hz tone reading every seconds
Body size	15.5mm * 12mm*5.5mm
Operational Voltage	3-5v
Max Current During Measuring	2.5mA
Pin number	4

A DC motor is a device that converts dc power into mechanical energy. Its principle of operation is that, when a current-carrying conductor is placed in a magnetic field, the conductor will experience a mechanical force. The direction of this force is given by Fleming's left-hand rule. The types include; Shunt-wound, Series wound and Compound wound. The parts of a dc motor include; Armature, commutator, brushes, axle, permanent magnet and a dc power supply. Figure 4 shows an image of a DC motor.

Fig. 4. A DC Motor

A LED as shown in Figure 5 is a semiconductor device that produces visible light of a specified colour. It is essentially different from conventional light sources such as fluorescent and incandescent. Its advantages include; does not produce infrared radiation and ultraviolet rays. It is mercury-free and can endure impact and vibrations.

Fig. 5. A LED

The various specifications and features of the Arduino Uno is shown in Table III.

TABLE III. SPECIFICATIONS AND FEATURES OF ARDUINO UNO

Microcontroller	ATmega328
Operating Voltage	5V
Input Voltage (recommended)	7-9V
Input Voltage (limits)	6-20V
Digital I/O Pins	14 (of which 6 provide PWM output)
Analog Input Pins	6
DC Current per I/O Pin	40 mA
DC Current for 3.3V Pin	50 mA
Flash Memory	32 KB (ATmega328) (0.5 KB used by bootloader)
SRAM	2 KB (ATmega328)
EEPROM	1 KB (ATmega328)
Clock Speed	16 MHz

B. Block Diagram

Figure 6 shows the block diagram of the automated drying line system. The hardware design entails two main components which are the connections between Arduino UNO and the DHT11 sensors and Arduino Uno and servo motto. When the system is in operation, the DHT11 senses the humidity and sends a signal to the Arduino Uno. If the humidity is high, the fun is turned on and together with the heat from the sunshine, the clothes are dried. If the humidity, falls below the threshold, the fun goes off and the LED and buzzer are turned on to inform the user that the clothes are dried.

Fig. 6. Block Diagram of Automated Drying Line

C. Hardware Architecture

The hardware architecture displaying the various components and their interconnection is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Hardware Architecture of Automated Drying Line System

D. Hardware Design Description

The designed system has two main components namely, a tube that direct sun rays into the system and a box-like structure that keep clothes. The tube has an inlet that is covered with a converging lens to direct sun rays onto a reflecting surface inclined at an angle of 45 degrees. The reflecting surface, in turn, focuses the sun rays onto the outlet of the tube which is covered with a diverging lens. The diverging lens ensures that the sun rays are evenly distributed within the system. The second component of the system is a box-like structure that accommodates the washed clothes. It has vent holes to allow vapour to escape whiles the clothes dry. It also has an orifice to allow drops of water from clothes to be collected. The interior surfaces of the box are coated black to retain heat from the sunrays to expedite the drying process of the clothes. Figure 8 shows a pictorial view of the designed system.

Fig. 8. Diagram of Designed Automated Drying Line System.

E. Software Design

The software of the paper is based on the flow chart in Figure 9. When the system is in use, the DHT11 will measure the humidity within the system. If it exceeds the threshold value (X). It means clothes have been hanged in it. The fan can be turned on by the user while clothes go through the drying process. If the humidity falls below the threshold value (X), then the LED and buzzer are turned on to prompt the user that the clothes are dried. The fan is automatically turned off if it was turned on. Figure 10 shows the pseudocode for the flow chart.

Fig. 9. Flow Chart of Automated Drying Line System

Fig. 10. Pseudo Code for Automated Drying Line System

IV. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND PROTOTYPING

This chapter provides a detailed description of the functionalities of the system, the building of a prototype, the hardware components used and the results that were derived. In designing the system, the hardware components were adequately tested to ensure that all work accurately before use.

A. Part List

The components used in this paper were all procured locally in Ghana. They are efficient and less expensive. Table IV provides the list of items procured and their corresponding costs.

TABLE IV. COST ANALYSIS OF COMPONENTS

COMPONENT	UNITS	COST (GHC)
Arduino Uno	1	70.00
Jumper wires	10	5.00
Lens	2	70.00
Mirror	1	1.00
Switch	1	1.00
LED	2	1.00
Bursar	1	2.00
DHT sensor	1	5.00
DC motto	1	3.00
Total		158.00

B. Circuit Design

The DHT sensor, motto, and LED were connected to the various pins on the Arduino board. The circuit was designed using Fritzing circuit design software. Figure 11 shows the diagram of the prototype.

Fig. 11. Circuit Diagram of Automated Drying Line System

C. System Implementation

The DHT11 sensor is connected to the Arduino using the pin configuration in Table V. The code written for the Arduino Uno can communicate with the DHT sensor via the serial communication functions provided by the Arduino library. Similarly, the LED, dc motor and buzzer were all connected to the Arduino and were fixed on the bread-board as shown in Figure 12 for easy communication.

TABLE V. PIN ALLOCATION OF THE ARDUINO TO THE RESPECTIVE COMPONENTS

Component	Pin
DHT11	2
Buzzer	5
Dc motto	9
LED (Red)	7
LED (Green)	6

Fig. 12. Breadboard with Components

D. Programming

The whole paper with its testing was done in C programming language using the Arduino IDE. Figures 13 shows a screenshot of the programming interface.

```
Real_Automated_Drying_Line_System | Arduino 1.8.8
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
Upload
Real_Automated_Drying_Line_System

int in1 =9;
int in2=8;
int button=10;
int button_state=0;
#include "DHT.h"
#define DHTPIN 2 // Digital pin connected to the DHT sensor
#define Led_Red 7
#define Led_Green 6
#define DHTTYPE DHT11 // DHT 11
#define Buzzer 5
#define fan 9
DHT dht(DHTPIN, DHTTYPE);
#include <Servo.h>
Servo myservo; // create servo object to control a servo
int pos = 0;
void setup() {
  Serial.begin(9600);
  // myservo.attach(9);
  pinMode(in1, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(in2, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(button, INPUT);
  Serial.println(F("DHTxx test!"));
  pinMode(Led_Red, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(Led_Green, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(Buzzer, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(fan, OUTPUT);
  dht.begin();
}
void TurnMotorA(){
  digitalWrite(in1, HIGH);
  digitalWrite(in2, LOW);
}
```

Fig. 13. Arduino Sketch ID

E. Prototype Building

The prototype for the automated drying line system was built with a breadboard, hand lens, paper glue and cardboards. The components were connected with the help of the circuit diagrams. Figures 14 and 15 show the prototype building and testing respectively.

Fig. 14. Prototype Building

Fig. 15. Prototype Building

F. Prototype Testing

The system was tested as shown in Figures 16, 17, 18 and 19.

Fig. 16. Prototype Testing

Fig. 17. Prototype Testing

Fig. 18. Prototype testing

Fig. 19. Prototype Testing

G. System Integration

The automated drying line system has been successfully integrated as shown in Figures 20, 21 and 22

Fig. 20. System Integration

Fig. 21. System Integration

Fig. 22. System Integration

- An improved means of informing users of the dryness of clothes can be considered.

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V. CONCLUSION AND REFUTURE WORK

In this paper, an automated drying line system has been designed and implemented. A prototype of the system has also been built which indicates a much more improved way for drying clothes. With this system, theft, strong winds, stains, among others are dealt with.

The following are recommended:

- The system can be improved to detect whether clothes are dried in it or not before measuring humidity;
- Lid that covers converging lens can be automated; and